

Supporting Information Text S4: Data handling

All data were analyzed and visualized with R (R Core Team, 2023) and PowerPoint, with packages dplyr (Wickham, François, et al., 2023), tidyr (Wickham, Vaughan, et al., 2023), forcats (Wickham, 2023), ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016), ggrepel (Slowikowski, 2023), gridExtra (Auguie, 2017), ggpattern (FC et al., 2022), factoextra (Kassambara & Mundt, 2020), vegan (Oksanen et al., 2022), metafor (Viechtbauer, 2010) and goeveg (von Lampe & Schellenberg, 2023).

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Bibliography

- Auguie, B. (2017). *gridExtra: Miscellaneous Functions for “Grid” Graphics*. R package version 2.3. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=gridExtra>
- FC, M., Davis, T. L., & Wickham, H. (2022). *ggpattern: “ggplot2” Pattern Geoms*. R package version 1.0.1. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=ggpattern>
- Kassambara, A., & Mundt, F. (2020). *factoextra: Extract and Visualize the Results of Multivariate Data Analyses*. R package version 1.0.7. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=factoextra>
- Oksanen, J., Simpson, G. L., Blanchet, F. G., Kindt, R., Legendre, P., Minchin, P. R., O’Hara, R. B., Solymos, P., Stevens, M. H. H., Szoecs, E., Wagner, H., Barbour, M., Bedward, M., Bolker, B., Borcard, D., Carvalho, G., Chirico, M., De Caceres, M., Durand, S., ... Weedon, J. (2022). *vegan: Community Ecology Package*. R package version 2.6-4. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=vegan>
- R Core Team. (2023). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*. R Foundation for Statistical Computing. <https://www.R-project.org/>
- Slowikowski, K. (2023). *ggrepel: Automatically Position Non-Overlapping Text Labels with “ggplot2”*. R package version 0.9.4. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=ggrepel>
- Viechtbauer, W. (2010). Conducting meta-analyses in R with the metafor package. In *Journal of Statistical Software* (Vol. 36, Issue 3, pp. 1–48). 10.18637/jss.v036.i03
- von Lampe, F., & Schellenberg, J. (2023). *goveg: Functions for Community Data and Ordinations*. R package version 0.6.5. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=goveg>
- Wickham, H. (2016). *ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis*. Springer-Verlag New York. <https://ggplot2.tidyverse.org>
- Wickham, H. (2023). *forcats: Tools for Working with Categorical Variables (Factors)*. R package version 1.0.0. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=forcats>
- Wickham, H., François, R., Henry, L., Müller, K., & Vaughan, D. (2023). *dplyr: A Grammar of Data Manipulation*. R package version 1.1.4. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=dplyr>
- Wickham, H., Vaughan, D., & Girlich, M. (2023). *tidyr: Tidy Messy Data*. R package version 1.3.0. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=tidyr>